

ACUTE TOXICITY AND CUMULATIVE PROPERTIES OF C-4 COMPOSITION: AN IN VIVO STUDY ON MICE

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Abstract. *These studies assessed the acute toxicity and cumulative properties of composition C-4, obtained from supramolecular complexes of amino acids and phenols with monoammonium salt of glycyrrhizic acid. The results showed that with a single intragastric administration to animals, composition C-4, according to acute toxicity indicators, belongs to class VI - relatively harmless chemical compounds, and with a single intraperitoneal administration to mice - to class V - practically non-toxic chemical compounds. With long-term administration of composition C-4 to mice in order of increasing doses and creating conditions for chronic poisoning, its cumulative coefficient was $Kk = 12.4$ ($Kk > 5$), while it was established that composition C-4 has weak cumulateness and according to the cumulative hazard level belongs to class 4 - low-hazard chemical substances.*

Keywords: *composition, glycyrrhizic acid, acute toxicity, cumulateness.*

Introduction

In recent years, the problem of drug safety has become one of the most pressing in global healthcare. This is due to the emergence of many drugs with high biological activity. One of the pressing problems of bioorganic chemistry today is the use of modern methods for creating drugs with high biological efficiency, low dosage, low toxicity and a small number of side effects. These problems can be solved with the help of nanopharmacology, which uses drug delivery systems in the form of nanoparticles of various natures. Currently, the method of complexation of biologically active substances with a carrier, which is used to create new drugs, is rapidly developing. In this area, the use of glycyrrhizic acid as a "carrier" of active components has become widespread [11,14]. Scientists at our institute have developed composition C-4 based on supramolecular complexes of amino acids and polyphenols with monoammonium salt of glycyrrhizic acid. In this study, the acute toxicity and cumulative properties of composition C-4 were assessed.

It is increasingly acknowledged that important indicator of drug safety is its acute toxicity. Acute toxicity is the ability of chemicals to cause damage or death of biological systems when administered once in high doses. The essence of this concept is that the toxic effect of chemicals can manifest itself at all levels of the structure of a biological object - from subcellular to population. This condition is characterized by disturbances in cellular metabolism and manifests itself in various pathological processes, such as disruption of energy metabolism, protein synthesis and cell division, activation of free radicals in the cell, and damage to the cell membrane. The

results of assessing the acute toxicity of drugs, determined with a single administration, play an important role in substantiating the doses selected to determine their toxicity upon repeated administration, as well as in determining their specific toxicity [7]. The cumulative properties of newly developed drugs are an important safety indicator determined upon their repeated administration. These substances can cause a sudden explosion of unfavorable factors arising from their accumulation in the most vulnerable systems, organs and tissues of the body. Therefore, the assessment of the cumulative effect of drugs is of great importance for determining their safe therapeutic doses for use in clinical practice. The results of these studies also allow us to assess the feasibility of continuing to study the composition C-4 [1,3,9].

The aim of the study is to assess the characteristics of the acute toxic and cumulative effects of the composition C-4 on the body of experimental animals.

Materials and methods of the study

Determination of acute toxicity. Determination of the acute toxicity of the composition C-4 was carried out using generally accepted pharmacotoxicological methods [6]. The experiments were conducted on healthy sexually mature white male mice weighing 20 ± 2.0 g, quarantined for at least 10-14 days, without open wounds and abrasions on the body. Each group included six animals. All animals were kept in the same conditions - with free access to water and food. The experiments were conducted by introducing composition C-4 into the stomach and abdominal cavity of animals, and the acute toxicity parameters were determined using the Litchfield and Wilcoxon method. In the first part of the experiment, composition C-4 was introduced into the stomach of mice at doses of 4000, 5000, 6000, 8000 mg/kg as a 10% solution once and in 2 doses for 1 hour at a dose of 10000 mg/kg. LD₅₀ — the median lethal dose — when introducing the composition into the stomach was determined according to the classification of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) [12]. In the second part of the experiment, composition C-4 was introduced intraperitoneally at doses of 800, 1000, 1300, 1600, 2000 mg/kg as a 5–10% solution. For intraperitoneal administration of compound S-4, the median lethal dose LD₅₀ was calculated using an online calculator, and its toxicity class was determined according to the modified IYoTT classification [2, 13].

Each dose of the drug was tested on 6 mice, which were observed for 14 days. On the first day of the experiment, the animals were observed in laboratory conditions every hour, recording their general condition, tremors, convulsions, as well as survival and possible death. On the remaining days of the experiment, the general condition and activity of the animals, behavioral characteristics, frequency and depth of breathing, the condition of the fur, skin and tail, as well as the consistency and amount of feces, frequency of urination and changes in body weight as indicators of the functional state of the body were recorded.

Determination of the therapeutic index

The therapeutic index (TI) was calculated using the following formula:

$$TI = LD_{50} / TD \quad [4]$$

Where: LD₅₀ is the median lethal dose, TD is the therapeutic dose (TD) determined by the same method (intra-gastric administration) to an animal of the same species.

Evaluation of cumulative properties

Experiments to study the cumulative properties of composition C-4 were conducted on 10 male mice under conditions of long-term exposure according to the method of R.K. Lim et al., kept in the same conditions - free access to water and food. In our previous study, the median lethal dose of composition C-4, determined with a single intra-gastric administration $LD_{50_1} > 10000$

mg/kg, was: 0.1; 0.15; 0.22; 0.34; 0.50; 0.75; 1.12 fractions, administered into the stomach of mice in increasing order every four days for 28 days. The cumulative coefficient of the composition of C-4 – K_k was calculated using the following formula [6]:

$$K_k = LD_{50_n} / LD_{50_1},$$

where: LD_{50_n} is the average lethal dose after n-fold administration; LD_{50_1} is the average lethal dose after a single administration. The degree of cumulativeness of the composition was determined using the modification of the scale by L.I. Medved and co-authors B.I. Lyublina: extremely cumulative (class 1, $K_{cum} < 1$); pronounced cumulative (class 2, $K_{cum} = 1-3$); moderate cumulative (class 3, $K_{cum} = 3.1-5$); weakly cumulative (class 4, $K_{cum} > 5$) [5].

Results. After the first day of the experiment, the animals were orally administered composition C-4 in doses of 4000, 6000, 8000 and 10000 mg/kg. The condition of the animals in laboratory conditions was monitored every hour, noting the appearance of vomiting, accumulation of food and the sedative effect of the composition (Table 1).

Table 1

Indices of acute toxicity of the composition C-4 upon oral administration to mice

Composition	Groups, Doses mg/kg	Dead animals/ total number	LD_{50} , mg/kg toxicity class
C-4	4000	0/6	>10000 VI class
	5000	0/6	
	6000	0/6	
	8000	0/6	
	10000	0/6	

By the end of the experiment, the general condition and activity of all animals in the vivarium, behavioral characteristics, frequency and depth of respiration, condition of the tail, fur and skin, as well as the consistency of feces, its quantity, frequency of urination and changes in body weight were within normal limits, no deaths of animals were recorded.

According to the obtained results, it was concluded that the average lethal dose of composition C-4 is $LD_{50} > 10,000$ mg/kg, where: according to the toxicity classification of Hodge and Sterner (1943), composition C-4 belongs to class V - practically non-toxic substances ($LD_{50} = 5000-15,000$ mg/kg) [10]; and according to the classification of the International Organization for Standardization (2001) - to class VI - relatively harmless substances ($LD_{50} > 5000$ mg/kg) [12].

In the second part of the experiment, after intraperitoneal administration of the C-4 composition to mice at doses of 800, 1000, 1300, 1600 and 2000 mg/kg, tachycardia, facial flushes and tremors were observed in some animals after 30–60 minutes. When the composition was administered to mice at a dose of 800 mg/kg, no deaths were recorded during the entire experiment (Table 2).

Table 2

Indices of acute toxicity of the C-4 composition upon intraperitoneal administration to mice

Composition	Groups, Doses mg/kg	Dead animals/ total number	LD_{50} , toxicity class
C-4	800	0/6	1153,6 mg/kg V class
	1000	2/6	
	1300	4/6	

	1600	5/6	
	2000	6/6	

When the S-4 composition was administered in doses of 1000, 1300, 1600 and 2000 mg/kg, mortality was recorded in these groups in a dose-dependent manner during the experiment, in which: more than half of the mice at a dose of 1300 mg/kg - 66.6%, at doses of 1600 and 2000 mg/kg - 83.3%, respectively; Up to 100% animal mortality was observed. Based on the obtained results, when S-4 composition was administered intraperitoneally to mice in doses of 800, 1000, 1300, 1600 and 2000 mg/kg, its average lethal dose exceeded LD50=708-1200 mg/kg, and according to the online calculator, it was found that LD50 = 1153.6 mg/kg [13], (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Dose-dependent mortality curve for a single intraperitoneal injection of C-4 to calculate LD50

According to the modified ITT classification [8], the C-4 composition was found to belong to the V class of chemicals for acute toxicity - almost non-toxic compounds - when administered once into the abdominal cavity of mice [2, 13].

In previous studies, the therapeutic dose determined by the introduction of the C-4 composition into the stomach of mice was 20 mg/kg [8]. In this case:

$$TI = \frac{>10\ 000\ \text{mg/kg}}{20\ \text{mg/kg}} = >500$$

It was determined that the TI - therapeutic index of the composition C-4 is higher than 500.

Another important study - in tests to assess the cumulative properties of the composition C-4, this composition was administered to the stomach of mice for 28 days according to the scheme given in Table 3. In acute toxicity experiments, the accumulation coefficient - Kk was calculated based on the LD50₁ > 10000 mg/kg determined after a single administration of the composition C-4 to the stomach of mice. The cumulative dose of the composition C-4 administered to mice during the entire experiment was 124000 mg/kg, and no animal deaths were observed until the end of the experiment, and based on this indicator, we concluded that the average lethal dose of the composition with multiple administration to mice is LD50_n > 124000 mg/kg. Kk = 124000 mg/kg / 10000 mg/kg = 12.4 of S-4 composition, it can be seen that Kk > 5.

Table 3

Results of evaluation of cumulative properties of composition S-4 when injected into the stomach of mice

days of entry	number of animals (n=10)	LD ₅₀ taken from	LD ₅₀ =10000 mg/kg
1-4	0/10	0,1	1000
5-8	0/10	0,15	1500
9-12	0/10	0,22	2200
13-16	0/10	0,34	3400
17-20	0/10	0,50	5000
21-24	0/10	0,75	7500
25-28	0/10	1,12	11200

It has been demonstrated that the cumulation coefficient of the C-4 composition was $K_k=12.4$, and the level of $K_k>5$ [5].

Considering all aspects examined throughout the research, it is evident that results obtained showed that the C-4 composition, obtained on the basis of supramolecular complexes of amino acids and phenols with monoammonium salt of glycyrrhizic acid, with a single administration to animals through the stomach, belongs to the VI class of acute toxicity - relatively harmless chemical compounds, and with a single administration of this composition into the abdominal cavity of mice - to the V class of acute toxicity - practically harmless chemical compounds. The subchronic toxicity index of the C-4 composition was also determined - the cumulation coefficient of $K_k=12.4$, and the level of $K_k>5$, based on these indicators it was determined that the composition has a weak cumulative property.

CONCLUSION

1. With a single intragastric administration of the C-4 composition to mice, LD₅₀ was $>10,000$ mg/kg and belonged to the VI class of acute toxicity - relatively harmless chemical compounds. With intraperitoneal administration of this composition to mice, LD₅₀ was $=1153.6$ mg/kg and belonged to the V class of acute toxicity - practically harmless chemical compounds.

2. It was established that the TI - therapeutic index of the C-4 composition exceeds 500.

3. With repeated administration of the C-4 composition to mice in increasing doses, creating conditions for chronic poisoning, its cumulation coefficient was $K_c = 12.4$ ($K_c>5$), which indicates weak cumulation of the C-4 composition and its cumulative hazard, belonging to the 4th class of low-hazard chemical substances.

Thus, the results of assessing the acute toxicity and cumulative properties of composition C-4, developed on the basis of supramolecular complexes of amino acids and polyphenols with monoammonium salt of glycyrrhizic acid obtained from a local plant, are of great importance for selecting effective doses for studying its biological activity, as well as for determining safe therapeutic doses for repeated or long-term use of the composition in clinical practice. The obtained results on the safety indicators of composition C-4, developed on the basis of supramolecular complexes of amino acids, polyphenols with monoammonium salt of glycyrrhizic acid, make it possible to continue the development and study of this composition.

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